

Child Trafficking and Sale of Children

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Abstract

Child trafficking, including commercial sexual exploitation (CSE), is one of the fastest growing and most lucrative criminal activities in the world. The global enslavement of children affects countless numbers of victims who are trafficked within their home countries or transported away from their homes and treated as commodities to be bought, sold, and resold for labor or sexual exploitation. All over the world, girls are particularly likely to be trafficked into the sex trade: Girls and women constitute 98% of those who are trafficked for CSE. Health and safety standards in exploitative settings are generally extremely low, and the degree of experienced violence has been linked with adverse physical, psychological, and social-emotional development. The human-rights-based approach to child trafficking provides a comprehensive conceptual framework whereby victim-focused and law enforcement responses can be developed, implemented, and evaluated.

Introduction

Trafficking of children is a form of human trafficking and is defined as the “recruitment, transportation, transfer, harboring, and receipt” of a child for slavery, forced labor and exploitation. This definition is substantially wider than the same document’s definition of “trafficking in persons. Children may also be trafficked for adoption.

The first major international instrument dealing with the trafficking of children is part of the 2000 United Nations Palermo protocols, titled the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons, especially Women and Children. The definition for child trafficking given here applies only to cases of trafficking that are transnational and involve organized criminal groups; in spite of this, child trafficking is now typically recognized well outside these parameters. The International Labour Organization expands upon this definition by asserting that movement and exploitation are key aspects of child trafficking. The definition of “child” used here is that listed in the 1989 U.N. Convention on the Rights of the Child which states, “a child means every human being below the age of 18 years, unless, under the law applicable to the child, majority is attained earlier. The distinction outlined in this definition is important, because some countries have chosen to set the “age of majority” lower than 18, thus influencing exactly what legally constitutes child trafficking.

Types of Trafficking

Types of Child Trafficking

Child Trafficking has been classified into different categories. Here is a look at some types of child trafficking in detail:

Domestic Slave

Children and their families in the rural areas are often tricked for the lure of higher wages in the cities. In reality the children are sold for certain amount and are forced to work as house help for no wages at all. In most of the child marriages young females are exploited as domestic slave and sexually assaulted. Such crimes are hardly ever exposed as they take place in private homes.

Child Labour

Children from rural areas often migrate or are trafficked for employment in industries like hotels and restaurants, construction industries, spinning mills etc. Victims are also physically and mentally exploited. They are forced to work for very low or no wages at all under threatening conditions.

Bonded Labour

Bonded labors are the labors that are forced to pay the family debt. Parents give away their children when they are unable to pay debts. Also children are sold for some amount due to poverty and lack of basic resources.

Sexual Exploitation

Sexual Exploitation is the bitter truth in rural as well as urban areas in India. Young females are trafficked and are forced to work as prostitute. Children are also exploited for commercial sex for the exchange of drugs, food, shelter etc. Unwanted pregnancy, HIV, STD's and even deaths are the common after-effects faced by these victims.

Illegal Activities

Children are also trafficked for illegal activities such as begging and organ trade as they are more sympathized by people as weak. In some unfortunate conditions, their body parts are damaged or cut off by the criminals as those injured make more money.

Trafficking for Organs

Demand for organs is higher than supply. This results in the illegal trade of organs and trafficking. Organs such as eyes and kidneys in particular are high in demand. There are criminal groups that exploit children for personal profits. Child organ trafficking is a dark reality in today's world.

Child Soldiers

Many children under the age group of 18 are trafficked and are being exploited as child soldiers. Other children are also forced to work as guards, cooks, servants etc. The children are forced to work hard as a result they are deprived from the childhood, love and care of their families.

Child Trafficking: Supply and Demand

Supply: Those who are trafficked compose the supply. The various supply factors are poverty, natural disasters, unemployment, domestic violence etc.

Demand: The traffickers and those who benefit from the child exploitation provide the demand. The most common demand factors are migrations, demand for cheap labor, organ trade, sex tourism, brothels, organized crime etc.

Effects of Child Trafficking

Isolation

Children trafficked are moved away from the family environment and are departed from the shield of love, care and protection by parents. They have to work under hazardous conditions and are exploited in several ways. Child trafficking is child abuse and has shattering and traumatic impact on a child. There is no one they can turn up to in such trauma.

Education

Most of the children trafficked are from poor and uneducated families where children support their families for income; they hardly ever go to school. Such children are tricked by traffickers for the lure of high wages and are transported to other destinations to work in industries for cheap wages or are sold for some amount. Young Girls are forced into prostitution and the work environment in the sex organizations is such that restricts child’s mental growth. Girls are sexually assaulted and are not encouraged for education.

Physical Health

Child trafficking victims experience inhumane living conditions, Poor diet and hygiene, physical abuse and beating and are deprived of the basic health care rights. Some of them are used for organ trade; others get injured at workplace. Children sexually assaulted are at the risk of unwanted pregnancies, sexually transmitted diseases, infections and abortions. Acid is poured into the eyes of some children to blind them for begging as they make more money. The life of the victims is always in danger in such working conditions.

Behavior

Victims of child trafficking have adverse behavior signs. Their voices are shut and hearts wounded which affects their relationship with others. Some might isolate themselves and cause harm and pain to oneself physically. They might get panic and anxiety attacks. Some may also excuse the reality by taking drugs and alcohol. Victims may loss interest in life and might try to escape away or commit suicide.

Causes of Child Trafficking

Girls as the Object of Desire

Girls are often seen as the objects of desire and demand from customers for young girls in prostitution is much higher, as a result female children are bought and sold for prostitution and sexual exploitation.

Unemployment

Unemployment rate in India is high due to which there are less financial opportunities. To support family needs or under pressure of family members children are bound to work. Often they are tricked for work and subjected to slavery, begging and sexual exploitation. Children from rural areas in poor condition are trafficked to cities for employment in industries such as spinning mills, hotels, restaurants, and construction for little or no pay at all. They are often physically and mentally exploited by the employers and have to work under hazardous conditions.

Bonded Labour

Bonded labor is also known as debt labor. Some parents sell their children as bonded labor for cash or are bound by debt to force their children to work as a bonded labor. Children are forced to work as bonded labors or do domestic work to pay family debts.

Lack of Education and Awareness

Lack of education is the major reason for lack of awareness which makes families surrender to traffickers. Each year millions of children are born without any birth registration making it impossible to track in any system. These children become the easy target for child traffickers.

Poor Function of Laws

Child trafficking in India has also increased due to poor functioning of the law. Child traffickers are at lower risk as there is no serious action taken against them.

Natural Disasters

Natural disasters like earthquake or flood in a particular state or city is the time when traffickers are attracted. Traffickers can act as a relief worker and trick children by offering food, work or shelter. They exploit the children under extremely vulnerable condition. Children who lose their families in natural disasters are bound or forced by traffickers to take uncertain decisions.

Child Marriages

Many girls are forced by families or sold by traffickers for child marriage. In most cases the condition of girls in early marriages is like slaves. They are exploited physically and mentally.

Conclusion

Child trafficking is a fast-growing network and has to be stopped. Government has to work with the help of NGO's to develop, evaluate and implement laws and provisions to stop the crime. The exploiters have to be punished rather than the exploited. Creating awareness and educating people is important. We need to stop supporting the act by refraining from donating to the beggars on the street as helping them encourages the crime even more.

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